

Prospects of detection of lensed gravitational wave signals

Shashwat Singh

Sorbonne Université - Sciences et Ingénierie, Paris, France, 75006

1 Introduction

With the release of the first detection of the Gravitational waves (GWs) in 2015, the event, namely - GW150914, opened a new window to probe the universe. Since then, we have had ~ 90 statistically significant detections so far, of which 35 were from the first half of the O3 run [Abbott et al., 2021a]. The growth in the number of detections from the previous runs is a remarkable achievement in achieving mammoth engineering and scientific goals from detecting just three GW events from the initial runs to 35 with the O3a run. Not only this, the O3a run further deepened the GWs' spectrum of credible sources ranging from blackhole binaries (BHBH), neutron star binaries (NSB), and the probable neutron star blackhole binaries (NSBH) [Li et al., 2020], alongside giving an insight into the possible population and the corrections and constrains to the mass gap [Edelman et al., 2021]. The detections of GW170817 the first multimessenger detection, including the gravitational band as well, had perhaps maximized the scientific gains from allowing stricter constraints on the Equation of State (EOS) of the neutron star to a separate calculation of the Hubble constant. Expanding the detector network is also essential, along with increased sensitivity to extract the maximum possible information from the signals. Owing to the highly delicate detectors, if either one falls out of observing mode due to unusually high noise or waves intercept from a skylocation or polarization for which the detector is significantly less sensitive. In those cases, observation from the remaining two detectors will not reconstruct the event entirely unless observed from an electromagnetic counterpart or other associated information.

However, the GWs, just like electromagnetic (EM) waves, can be lensed due to the presence of the massive body in the line-of-sight (LOS) of the receiver (detector) and the source. Lensing can also be observed (especially in EM signals) if the effect of the intervening body (lens) is massive enough along with the center of Einstein radius (see sec - 2) not lying directly in the LOS of the detector. In that case, a part of the rays will have to travel a much larger distance, and will thus image will not be symmetric¹. This is observant and prominent in EM waves; however, for GWs (within the lens approximation; Sec-2), the wavelength is much larger than the characteristic size of a star, or a neutron star and is usually strongly lensed by a galaxy or a galaxy cluster. An excellent example of how the received image evolves for an EM signal such that the source at higher redshifts moves background to a $10^{12}M_{\odot}$ galaxy can be viewed from [Singh et al., 2020].

In this work, I aimed to explore the prospects of detection of galaxy lensed GWs with the upgrades planned for the next generation of detectors and the possible upgrades by the 2030s. This work is divided into sections wherein I have primarily laid down the basic theory and formulation required to understand lensed GWs and how they are different from their EM counterparts. Further, I describe the set of detectors I have used for the current study and the description of the source population targeted towards BBH signals only. However, one can do the entire study for NSBH and NSB by changing the population and the horizon detectability from the available repository: <https://github.com/SSingh087/Prospects-of-LGWs>

2 Gravitational wave lensing

When a massive body intervenes in the trajectories of propagating GWs, the waves deviate and curve (a phenomenon similar to electromagnetic, gravitational lensing). This deviation leads to the observation of multiple images of the same source from which GWs were emitted with varied amplitude and arrival times. The amplitude variation is due to focusing by lensing, and since the waves traverse different trajectories with the same speed, the arrival time is different. Unlike electromagnetic lensing, where the lensed image classification is based on the angular displacement of photons, for GW lensing, it is required to distinguish them using lensed GWs templates statistically.

¹The reader should note this only accounts the effect of string lensing

Figure 1: Illustration of the gravitational lens configuration in the thin lens approximation. The lensing configuration is described by the source displacement from the line-of-sight η , the angular diameter distance from the observer to the source D_S , to the lens D_L and from lens to the source D_{LS} and by the relative position of the image in the image plane ξ . Only h_+ polarization is shown in the image and h_\times is suppressed however the inclination as shown is face on thus the detectors will receive from both the polarizations (h_+ & h_\times) combined together to give a circular polarization.

In GW lensing, the effect produced induced by galaxy/galaxy cluster(s) ($\gtrsim 10^8 M_\odot$) is identified as strong lensing, whereas lensing induced by masses, M , $10^{-6} < \frac{M}{M_\odot} < 10^6$ are referred as weak lensing [Schneider, 2006a, Schneider, 2006b]. However, the detection capability for separating lensed signals from the same source is limited by millisecond time resolution. The detection and inference of lensed signals depend entirely on identifying the signals using the LGW templates. A comparison of lensed GWs templates with the non-lensed GWs template having the same intrinsic parameters and extrinsic parameters - luminosity distance (D_L), inclination(ι), polarization angle(ψ); is shown in Fig-2.

One can expect microlenses to be present in the path of strongly lensed signals, resulting in beating patterns due to the enhanced effect of microlenses on already strongly lensed signals. The beating pattern can be observed from the time-series signal generated in Fig-2b. Although not covered in this work, the amplitude and the repetition of the pattern can allow inferring properties of the lens.

For this project, I have worked within the geometrical optics approximations valid when the GW wavelength is much smaller than the characteristic size of the space-time curvature. Within this limit, the original GW from the source is focused on the observer from numerous distinct trajectories resulting in multiple images and, thereon, resulting in time delays. From Fig-1, the source η and its projected mass distribution $\sum(\xi) = \int \rho(\xi, z) dz$ (where $\rho(\xi, z)$ is the density of the lens at a given position (ξ, z)) on the image plane can be represented as

$$\eta = D_S \beta \quad (1)$$

$$\xi = D_L \theta \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla_\theta [0.5(\theta - \beta)^2 - \phi(\theta)] = 0 \quad (3)$$

Thus we can evaluate time delays, $t_{d,j}$ and image position, θ_j using the lens equation (Eq-3) where ∇_θ is the two-dimensional nabla operator with respect to θ , and $\phi(\theta)$ is the two-dimensional deflection potential. $\phi(\theta)$ can be evaluated from the two-dimensional Poisson equation $\nabla_\theta^2 \phi(\theta) = 2\kappa(\theta)$ where $\kappa = \sum(D_L \theta) / \sum_{cr}$, where \sum is the surface mass density of the lens and $\sum_{cr} = (c^2 / (4\pi)) D_S / (D_L D_{LS})$. Evaluating Eq-3 yields N different solutions, which give the image positions θ_j . Given the image positions θ_j , it is possible to retrieve the individual magnifications μ_j and time-delays $t_{d,j}$ for each image by direct substitution [Diego et al., 2019].

(a) Strongly lensed (\tilde{h}_+) and unlensed (h_+) h_+ polarized waveform of $30\text{-}30M_\odot$ BBHs on the same plot in timeseries. The lensed images differ by the magnification and the a time (zoomed out) delay of $\sim 13.4\text{s}$.
(b) Microlensed lensed (\tilde{h}_+) and unlensed (h_+) h_+ polarized waveform of $30\text{-}30M_\odot$ BBHs on the same plot in timeseries. Beating patterns are clearly visible.

(c) Strongly lensed (\tilde{h}_+) and unlensed (h_+) h_+ polarized waveform of $30\text{-}30M_\odot$ BBHs on the same plot in frequency-evolution-with-time. The lensed images differ by the magnification and the a time delay of $\sim 13.4\text{s}$.
(d) Microlensed lensed (\tilde{h}_+) and unlensed (h_+) h_+ polarized waveform of $30\text{-}30M_\odot$ BBHs on the same plot in frequency-evolution-with-time.

Figure 2: LGW templates.

3 Network of detectors

For this work, I have used various detector networks that include combinations of 2G and 3G detectors with sensitivities to be attained towards the end of 2030. For the LIGO detectors in Hanford (H), Livingston(L), and the planned detector in India (I), I used "Voyager" sensitivity. For Virgo (V) and KAGRA (K), I use the "O5 sensitivity curves" and design sensitivity, respectively.

For CE, designed to have ten times longer arms than the current LIGO design, which is to be built in progressing design sensitivity, at two sites, one in the USA and the other in Australia, choosing "CE1" sensitivity for the work [Hall and Evans, 2019, Abbott et al., 2017]. Longer arms will allow observing the increased amplitude of the signals with no increase in noise, resulting in high SNRs. The developments in CE will also allow increasing the observing bandwidth of the instrument [Essick et al., 2017]. ET is also a 3G planned detector with arms extending 10 km long and, similar to LISA, has a triangular design with effectively two detectors in each corner (Fig-3). ET will considerably limit the seismic noise's effect as an underground third-generation gravitational-wave observatory. Of the 3G designs, ET is designed to have high detectability for low-frequency targets. I have tabulated the detectors used for the current study in Table-1 with the same abbreviations used further in the article.

The combination that were used in this study are

- Two CE (sites in Australia and USA)
- Single ET only
- Two CE and single ET
- H, V, L, I, K
- All detectors - CE, ET, H, V, L, I, K

Abbreviation	Observatory	f_{low} (Hz)	Noise Curve	Latitude	Longitude
H	LIGO Hanford	10	Voyager	46.5	-119.4
L	LIGO Livingston	10	Voyager	30.6	-90.8
V	VIRGO	11	O5 High	43.6	10.5
I	LIGO India	10	Voyager	14.2	76.4
K	KAGRA	11	Design	36.4	137.3
CE ^U	Cosmic Explorer USA	5.2	CE1	40.8	-113.8
CE ^A	Cosmic Explorer AUS	5.2	CE1	40.8	-113.8
ET	Einstein Telescope	2	ET-D Design	43.6	10.5

Table 1: The location, noise curve, and low frequency cutoff flow used for the detector configurations considered.

(a) Sensitivity curves for the detectors used in the analysis. (b) The design shows how ET is numerically treated. It consists of three detectors at the same place, thus allowing low-frequency detections and localization capabilities which is unlike any ground-based detector. Black, yellow and red marks the three arms with purple as the mirror where the strain interference is measured.

Figure 3:

4 Software Used

Following the approach proposed by Pagano et al. in **LENSINGGW: a PYTHON package for lensing of gravitational waves** [Pagano et al., 2020] I developed a Python library **LENSGW**² whose framework is dependent on **lenstronomy - gravitational lensing software package** [Birrer and Amara, 2018] for finding lens images and solving lens potential (similar to the scheme used by **LENSINGGW**) and **PyCBC** [Nitz et al., 2020], for generating waveforms. As discussed in Sec-2, based on the type of lensing, images can also be separated into two categories: microimages and macroimages formed by stellar mass lenses ($M_l \lesssim 10^6 M_\odot$) and by a galaxy or a galaxy cluster ($M_l \gtrsim 10^6 M_\odot$). Stellar-mass lenses that are embedded within the galaxy or galaxy cluster produce microimages over the macroimage that can be resolved only up to separation as small as μas [Diego et al., 2019]. Thus while modeling the waveform, one needs to consider both cases of microlenses and macrolenses simultaneously.

In order to find the lensed images of a source, one has to solve the lens equation (Eq. (3)), which is a system of two non-linear, algebraic, coupled equations of two variables. In addition, the gravitational potential ϕ may not be analytic. Thus it is difficult to find a proper solution to the problem. As suggested by [Press et al., 1996] one can resolve this issue by giving the solver the initial values given to the algorithm are close enough to the actual images. This is the sole reason wherein lensing packages like **LENSTRONOMY** rely on a backward procedure: the image plane is tiled into pixels, whose centers (or edges, depending on the package) serve as a dummy input for θ in the lens equation. For a given potential, possible source positions are anticipated for each pixel (ray-shooting), and tiles hosting possible solutions are determined by comparing the source position predicted to the true one. When stellar-mass lenses are embedded into galaxies or galaxy clusters, microimages are likely to form on top of strongly lensed images which can be separated by as little as μas .

LENSGW differs from **LENSINGGW** slightly on how the inputs are taken and the waveform is generated. Since **LENSINGGW** directly generates strain timeseries data which from **LALSIm** that can be used further for analysis,

²<https://github.com/SSingh087/lensGW>

using LENS_{GW} generates two polarizations namely h_+ and h_\times allowing to generate strain signal using $h(t) = f_+ \times h_+ + f_\times \times h_\times$ where $h(t)$ is the strain and f_+ and f_\times are antenna pattern weights which can further be projected onto the detector. Giving individual level flexibility was the sole idea to generate this library. For this analysis I used TaylorF2 approximation, which uses the 2,2 dominant band and is accurate upto 3.5 PN term. The LENS_{GW} waveforms are made available to PyCBC environment using a PyCBC plugin³. The dependency chart can be visualized from <https://github.com/SSingh087/lensGW/blob/main/lensGW.png> for LENS_{GW} and <https://github.com/SSingh087/lensGW-PyCBC-plugin/blob/main/lgw.png> for LENSING_{GW}.

5 Population

I generated a population of $\sim 10^4$ BBH mergers of 30-30 M_\odot (detector frame masses) up to a D_L of 40000Mpc, which are distributed isotropically in orientation (ψ), inclination (ι) and skylocation (RA - α , DEC - δ) assuming a fiducial, local merger rate of $320Gpc^{-3}yr^{-1}$ consistent with the observational constraints from current GW search [Abbott et al., 2021b]. However, the merger increases with the redshift but slower than the star formation rate; I have assumed (at least for this study) that it follows the star formation rate as mentioned in [Madau and Dickinson, 2014]. In general, the GWs are not biased towards any direction or any orientation or inclination; however, the detectors are more sensitive towards some inclination $\sim [30^\circ, 60^\circ]$ due to the quadruple nature of GWs [Schutz, 2011]. Binaries that are face-on will have the amplitude contribution from both the polarizations (h_+ & h_\times) combined to give a circular polarization⁴. In contrast, face-off amplitude will have contributed only from one polarization (h_+).

Similar to unlensed BBH GW signals, lensed signals were generated based on similar assumptions of 30 – 30 M_\odot BBH up to a D_L of 40000Mpc, lensed by a point mass of $10^{12}M_\odot$ redshifted at $z_l = 1$. This idea assigns a similar probability of being lensed by a galaxy-like (typical galaxies lie between $\sim 10^8M_\odot - 10^{15}M_\odot$) body which is the main focus of this project. Thus this is not the most accurate case since galaxies tend to form in clusters and superclusters, and the abundance is also affected as one approaches higher redshift. There are indeed some libraries that generate galactic distribution based on the Cosmology used⁵. Similar work has been carried out by [Li et al., 2018]. In the most accurate scenario, a smaller fraction of lenses will be observed compared to this report. However, only those lensed BBH signals are considered for analysis that are at least 2 times the redshift of the lens; thus, the probability of a BBH merger signal getting lensed is not affected by the presence of another galaxy. However, it is suggestive to bias the lensed population corresponding to the galactic distribution for the closest accurate result.

Given the population and predictions corresponding to detectability of 30-30 M_\odot BBHs, the detection can be up to ~ 50 redshifts when considering the 3G detectors and upgrades.

6 Evaluation of SNR

For all the population, SNR was evaluated when observed from combination of detector networks mentioned in Sec-3. For the SNR of combined detectors (ρ_N), the SNR is just the sum of the power SNRs of the individual detectors (ρ_k) such that:

$$\rho_N = \left[\sum_{k=1}^{N_D} \rho_k^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where N_D is the number of detectors and ρ_k can be defined as

$$\rho_k = \left[2 \int_0^\infty \frac{|H_k(f)|^2}{S_h(f)} df \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where $H_k(f)$ is the waveform projected onto the k^{th} detector and $S_h(f)$ is the one-sided spectral noise density normalized to the gravitational wave amplitude [Schutz, 2011].

In the case of unlensed signals, the SNR peaked around a single value around the merger time, but for lensed signals, the SNR peaks around multiple values with some time delay if compared to the unlensed waveform. Thus to evaluate the SNR and do further analysis on the waveform, I separated the lensed waveform into two individual waveforms by observing the evolution of SNR. When the coherent SNR drops below the threshold value, which is 12 for the analysis, it is assumed it becomes dominated by noise, and no meaningful information can be extracted. Since we are using Gaussian noise and thus there are no chances of transients or the background signals. Thus when

³https://pycbc.org/pycbc/latest/html/waveform_plugin.html

⁴A nice visualization can be obtained from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F4stTzxYrN0>

⁵<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/1538-3881/152/6/228>

Figure 4: Population distribution of the BBH signals generated. The lensed BBH signals have the same parameters, given that they differ by a lensed parameter and its properties.

significant SNR is accumulated, a separate window is created for that particular image, and the SNR is evaluated for that individual window. In many instances, the images overlap. Thus, windows usually do not have equal lengths in time, which is not the usual case since strong lensing does not affect the duration of the signal (which in turn signifies that the intrinsic properties- redshifted masses are not changed from image to image). However, as mentioned above in Sec-2, there is a millisecond time resolution limit up to which one can resolve the images; therefore, this work needs attention in light of upcoming detectors and the LISA band where signals are bound to overlap [Pizzati et al., 2022]. This method also allows us to compare the SNRs directly with the unlensed images. We observe that fraction of BBH signals that are not detected due to the SNR threshold are detected by the lensed waveform due to magnification. We generally observe that a more significant fraction of only a single image is detected for such cases. However, lensing can generally allow observation of some weak signals due to magnification.

7 Result & Discussion

The number of sources that each combination of the detector can detect is highlighted in Fig-5. One can directly infer the lower detection rates due to the lensing compared to the unlensed signals. Alongside, we observe in some cases that the detector combination detects almost 100% of all the signals generated. Two factors play a crucial role in the detector network and the detectors within the network, the signal parameter (loudness, polarization (orientation), skylocation). For the second case (signal parameter), the signals received are from 30 – 30 M_{\odot} (detector frame) BBHs being isotropic in orientation and skylocation up to a distance of 40000Mpc⁶. Thus making it loud enough to be detected for the current set of detector networks, given a comparison made from the first detection of 30 – 30 M_{\odot} BBHs detected in 2015 with LVC sensitivity. Now for the first case - the detector network and the network's detectors are crucial factors in observing a confident signal. If one of the detectors either falls out of observing mode due to unusually high noise or waves intercept from a skylocation or polarization for which the detector is significantly less sensitive. In those cases, observation from the remaining two detectors will not reconstruct the event entirely unless observed from an electromagnetic counterpart or other associated information. For this work, I have chosen the network sensitivity (all detectors either include upgrades to the 3G detectors) and the signals such that it is loud enough to be detected.

We also observe in the same plot that the lensed signals have a much smaller % of detection, which is biased by the factor of lens approximation's validity. Only those signals are considered for an analysis whose source redshifts

⁶The BBH signals at higher redshift will have a much smaller mass in the source frame (BBH merger frame). Since cosmological redshifts cause the stretching of the signals' wavelength and, in turn, reduce the observed frequency, making it observed from the higher mass components. However, since our detector frame masses are fixed, the source frame masses for higher redshifts will be much smaller, governed by the formula $M_d = M_s(1+z)$ where M_d , M_s are detector frame, and source frame masses and z is the redshift

Figure 5: % of detections of the unlensed and lensed BBH signals with $30 - 30 M_{\odot}$ BBH up to a D_L of 40000Mpc, lensed by a point mass of $10^{12}M_{\odot}$ redshifted at $z_l = 1$.

are almost twice the redshifts of the lens. The population detection is also biased by the number of grids that the solver forms in an attempt to search for the images, which are not very fine (see Sec-4). Finer grids consume excess times to generate the image from the solver presented, even using optimization techniques⁷. For a general case of $\mathcal{O}(5)$ population, I have been running this on Kaggle⁸ however, a window of improvement is still open in this direction to generate waveforms. This problem is slightly tackled by making a first macro search on the coarse grid and then proceeding to resolve images within the grid that have possible image candidates. However, the solver still searches for all the grids centered around the possible image candidate. This is the sole reason the analysis presented from Fig-6 – Fig-10 is done for a smaller population.

From Fig-6 and Fig-7 evolution of SNR of unlensed signals with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalescence phase, for population of 10^4 and 10^2 respectively. The general observation from these plots is for the detector combination wherein all detectors are in observing mode. The signal has a significantly higher SNR and thus a higher detection rate. The SNR decreases as inverse square law with D_L , peaking for ι that are either 0 or 2π as explained in Sec-5. Other parameters α , δ , ψ , and coalescence phase do not strongly depend on the SNR and are isotropic. However, one can observe a slight bias for the SNR detected for δ such that the BBHs that form a solid angle for $\sim 60^\circ$ above and below the detector network horizon⁹.

Fig-8 - Fig-10 represents the evolution of SNR of sensed signals with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalescence phase, for population of 10^{210} lensed by a point mass of $10^{12}M_{\odot}$ redshifted at $z_l = 1$. The lensed signals have a much lower SNR - $\mathcal{O}(2)$ as compared to the SNR evolution of unlensed signals - $\mathcal{O}(3)$ (for the same population size). Also, Fig-8 represents the images that have overlapped and are not separable by the millisecond time resolution. The first image we obtained is the magnified one, and the second image is demagnified (negative magnification); thus, the order of SNR observed decreases to $\mathcal{O}(1)$. However, the data points observed are so less to do meaningful statistics or draw any inference from the second images. Moreover, the redshift cutoff reduces the population chosen for analysis; thus, I can report better results once the jobs running on Kaggle are complete.

8 Future works

Some of the improvements windows include checking the solver, and I have initiated some discussion with the collaborators regarding this issue. This will allow working with a more extensive population set and making meaningful inferences. This will also allow comparing lensed signals to unlensed signals directly in support of possible detection low SNR signals due to lensing. Another window is wherein the model only works for the Point mass type lens, and there can be plausible other geometries of lenses that can be used along with the impact of microlenses. This can allow the study of dark matter and constrain some of its properties. The polarization content of the lensed images is also an interesting phenomenon that can be used to steer the discussion towards testing GR theories; however, this is far-sighted work and needs extensive modeling, which is thus left for future work only.

⁷This issue is still under review

⁸<https://www.kaggle.com/astrocosmo>

⁹I am still unable to reason out this bias. It might be due to the population bias as observed in Fig-5 or some physical phenomenon I am not sure of

¹⁰simulations are still running on Kaggle for 10^4 population.

Figure 6: The evolution of SNR of unlensed signals with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalescence phase for population of 10^4 .

Figure 7: The evolution of SNR of unlensed signals with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalescence phase for population of 10^2 .

Figure 8: The evolution of SNR of lensed signals with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalscence phase for population of 10^2 .

Figure 9: The evolution of SNR of lensed signals (first image) with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalscence phase for population of 10^2 .

Figure 10: The evolution of SNR of lensed signals (second image) with various detector combinations corresponding to different parameters - D_L , ι , α , δ , ψ and coalascence phase for population of 10^2 .

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